

TRAUMA LITERATURE AND COLONIAL VIOLENCE: A POSTCOLONIAL ANALYSIS OF MANTO'S *A SPECTACLE*Wareesha Rukhsar^{*1}, Tehreem Shaheen², Mashal Javed³^{*1,2,3}COMSATS University Islamabad, Pakistan¹wareerukhsar@gmail.comDOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15689247>**Keywords**

colonial violence, Frantz Fanon, trauma literature, postcolonial studies

Article History

Received on 10 May 2025

Accepted on 10 June 2025

Published on 18 June 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Wareesha Rukhsar

Abstract

Trauma literature serves as a powerful medium to convey the brutality of colonialism, depicting the scars inflicted upon entire communities, cultures, and families. The perpetuation of colonial violence has led to profound human suffering, necessitating an examination of the lasting impact of colonialism on individual and collective identities. While significant scholarly attention has been devoted to analyzing the story in the light of Pre-Partition violence, there is a limited focus on exploring *A Spectacle* through the theoretical framework of colonial violence and how it serves as a piece of trauma Literature. Therefore, through the use of qualitative approach, this study aims to theoretically examine Saadat Hasan Manto's *A Spectacle* using Frantz Fanon's theory of Violence and identify its elements of trauma literature by analyzing the emotional and psychological wounds caused by colonial violence. The findings of the study reveal Saadat Hasan Manto's short story *A Spectacle* as an example of trauma literature, portraying the haunting impacts of colonial violence on individual and collective identities.

INTRODUCTION

Saadat Hasan Manto's *A Spectacle* can be taken as an appealing example of Trauma Literature in South Asia, within the context of historical colonial violence, specifically the Jallianwala Bagh massacre of 1919 and the British aerial bombing of Gujranwala. The story references the Jallianwala Bagh massacre (1919) that occurred in Amritsar, Punjab, under British colonial rule and the British bombing of Gujranwala, both traumatic historical events in colonial South Asia.

On that tragic day, thousands of unarmed civilians, including men, women, and children, gathered in Jallianwala Bagh, a public garden, to protest peacefully and celebrate the Baisakhi festival. Brigadier-General Reginald Dyer, without warning or prior notice to disperse, ordered his troops to open fire on the crowd, which resulted in killing and injuring thousands of

civilians. Manto looks back on how these events scarred not only individuals but also entire communities, particularly children who witness violence and carry its legacy. *A Spectacle* explores intergenerational, psychological, emotional, and societal trauma caused by colonial violence and oppression. In the colonial context, violence is more than physical brutality; it penetrates the psychological and social fabric of the colonized, leaving lasting scars on individual and collective consciousness.

The story, which revolves around a child whose innocence is shattered by the public execution of freedom fighters, not only depicts the horrors of colonial rule but also the collective trauma experienced by colonized subjects. It suggests how fiction can be taken as a means of bearing witness to unspeakable atrocities, also preserving the memory of

marginalized experiences that might otherwise be forgotten. By framing the work as trauma literature, this study employs Frantz Fanon's Theory of Violence to analyze the various types of pain caused by colonial oppression. The aim of this study is to theoretically analyze Saadat Hasan Manto's *A Spectacle* and identify its elements of trauma literature by analyzing the emotional and psychological wounds caused by colonial violence. Through this analysis, the study highlights the importance of literature in understanding the concepts of fragmented identity, resistance, and recovery. Moreover, *A Spectacle* contributes to postcolonial literature by highlighting the mechanisms of power, fear, and oppression employed by colonial regimes.

1. Thesis statement

This paper studies Saadat Hasan Manto's *A Spectacle* through the perspective of Fanon's theory of violence as systematic oppression, and resistance, suggesting that the text is an appealing piece of trauma literature, that portrays the emotional and psychological marks left by colonial oppression and communal violence.

2. Research Objectives

- To analyze the themes of trauma and distress in Manto's short story *A Spectacle*
- To use Fanon's theory of violence to analyze how Manto criticizes the dehumanizing impacts of colonialism and communal violence.

3. Research Questions

- How can *A Spectacle* be categorized as trauma literature of South Asia?
- How does Fanon's theory of Violence help to analyze the story's theme of dehumanizing impacts of colonial violence?

4. Literature Review

Aghamelu, Fidelis Chuka argues "Fanon notes that colonialism is violent in its natural state. In other words, he sees violence as the defining characteristic of colonialism". While further emphasizing the violence of colonial system, the researcher goes on saying "The natives are being exploited, enslaved, oppressed, marginalized, dehumanized, abused and devalued by the colonizers". A study by Mbembe (2003) elaborates on the concept of "necropolitics,"

where colonial powers exercised control over life and death, reducing the colonized to a state of subhuman existence. Indicating the multifaceted nature of violence, B. k. JHA says, "Though Fanon nowhere defines the term violence in clear-cut terms, he has used it in more senses than one. For example, he has used it in the sense of physical injury. This is one sense in which he refers to colonial regime as being created and maintained by violence." Zenon Ndayisenga in his article "Fanon on the Arbitrariness of Using Violence: An Inevitable for Both Colonialism and Decolonization" posits that colonizers and colonized both can never set for negotiation as "violence of the colonized intends to conquer and colonize while in contrast, the counter-violence from the colonized intervenes as means of self-defense and claims to reach a new human world that honors everyone in the society."

Edmund Burke while commenting on Frantz Fanon's "The Wretched Of the Earth" states that "The colonial world, we learn, is a Manichean world, a dualistic world, in which the settler stands for all that is good and the native for all that is evil. It is also a world built on violence-first on the bayonets of the conquering armies, then on the psychological violence inflicted on the native to keep him in his place by convincing him of his unworthiness". In response to the violence of colonization, Fanon argues for a counter-violence as an essential step toward liberation. Fanon, emphasizing the violence of liberation argues, "It frees the native from his inferiority complex and from his despair and inaction; it makes him fearless and restores his self-respect." Edmund further goes on saying " For a war of national liberation to be successful, violence must be disciplined to its needs; it cannot be left uncontrolled." Sacrificing one's life can only be the way to get freedom from oppressors, as in Hegel's (1971) words, "It is solely by risking life that freedom is obtained". Messay Kebede in 'The Rehabilitation of Violence and Violence of Rehabilitation' emphasizes the importance of risking life as "Violence expresses this disincarnate, ethereal freedom. It is how freedom exists less as an attribute than as the very subject exacting recognition through the risking of life." Reiland Rabaka argues "That "the native" "chooses" violence - self-defensive violence - as a means toward the end of "total liberation" should surprise no one, least of all colonialists, capitalists, and

those associated with the ruling race, ruling gender, and ruling class(es) of the modern (neo)imperial “world system.”

5. Research Methodology

This research employs the method of textual analysis by Catherine Belsey to examine Saadat Hasan Manto’s *A Spectacle* as a work of trauma literature. Textual analysis is a qualitative research method that involves a deep and critical reading of texts to disclose different layers of meaning, structure, and subtext. It allows researchers to engage deeply with the text, focusing on its themes, language, narrative strategies, and symbols, and relate these elements to larger theoretical frameworks.

This approach is utilized to examine how Manto portrays the psychological and emotional damage brought on by colonial violence in *A Spectacle*. To find signs of trauma and resistance, particular components like character development, dialogue, and vivid imagery will be examined. In light of Frantz Fanon’s theory of violence, a critical analysis will be conducted of the characters’ fragmented emotional states, the graphic representations of violence, and the brutal images of human suffering. Fanon’s theory provides an angle through which to view the story’s underlying pain, emphasizing the dehumanizing and destructive aspects of colonial violence. This study attempts to reveal how Manto criticizes systematic oppression and demonstrates its enduring effects on the human psyche by juxtaposing the text with Fanon’s views.

6. Theoretical Framework

This research uses Frantz Fanon’s theory of violence, a basic concept within postcolonial theory, to critically investigate Saadat Hasan Manto’s *A Spectacle*. The postcolonial theory according to John Lye’s ‘*Contemporary Literary Theory*,’ “Postcolonial theory is also built around the concept of resistance, of resistance as subversion, or opposition, or mimicry – but with the haunting problem that resistance always inscribe the resist into the texture of the resisting: It is a two-edged sword. As well, the concept of resistance carries with it or can carry with it ideas about human freedom, liberty, identity, individuality, etc.” In the context of Postcolonial theory, trauma literature can be categorized as the writings that explore the

collective and individual sufferings of the colonized, whose identities are fragmented by systematic violence and cultural erasure.

Key theorists, including Edward Said, Gayatri Spivak, and Homi K Bhabha, while studying postcolonial theory, examined how colonial powers exploited, marginalized, and dehumanized colonized societies, resulting in cultural hegemony, psychological disintegration, hybridity, and the marginalization of subaltern voices. Edward Said’s elaboration of the concepts such as ‘orient, the other’ and ‘occident’ in ‘*Orientalism*,’ while Bhabha’s theory of Mimicry and Hybridity as well as Spivak’s ‘*Can the Subaltern Speak?*’ point out the aftermaths of colonial rule and its oppression. Homi K. Bhabha focuses on concepts like hybridity and mimicry, explaining how colonized cultures blend their identity by mixing their traditions with colonial influences. Edward Said introduces the concept of “*Orientalism*,” where Western powers construct stereotypical images of Eastern societies to assert control and justify domination. Gayatri Spivak examines the silencing of marginalized voices, coining the term “subaltern” to describe those who are excluded from power.

Fanon’s work can be aligned with these concepts by relating the practice of violence in the colonial and postcolonial experience. For Fanon, the colonized must confront the structural violence of colonial systems, even if it means physical resistance to reclaim their identity. The psychological, cultural, and physical impacts of colonial violence and its subsequent manifestations in the decolonization process are the basis of Fanon’s theory of Violence. Fanon’s major work, *The Wretched of the Earth*, emphasizes that colonialism is fundamentally violent, not only in its direct imposition of force but also in its psychological and cultural oppression. This violence, according to Fanon, requires an equally forceful reaction from the colonized as they struggle for liberation. Fanon argues that colonial violence results in a fractured sense of self and so the colonized internalize that trauma. As a result, as an act of catharsis, the colonized are supposed to become violent, whether physically or mentally, so they can reclaim their lost identity in one way or another.

This concept can be related to the Postcolonial trauma narrative, like Manto’s *A Spectacle*, where the colonizers publicly executed and shot those who

showed resistance. However, the colonized even a little child was having these thoughts of getting revenge. The dehumanizing violence in the story depicts the brutal rule of the British regime, where liberation, as Fanon suggests, becomes a challenging task; however, it can be achieved through resistance.

7. Analysis and Discussion

The analysis of the short story *A Spectacle* focuses on the text that contains the use of several literary and narrative devices, the portrayal of characters, and the use of language to depict the cold atmosphere of colonial oppression. The postcolonial theoretical concept of violence and oppression will be explored while carrying out the textual analysis of the story. Since the main character of the story is a child who is experiencing, along with other characters, different types of psychological and emotional traumas in colonial oppression, the analysis will also focus on examining the text as trauma literature of South Asia.

7.1. Narrative Style of the text

The text of the story *A Spectacle* is a compelling narrative that investigates the turmoil of a violent colonial regime through the usage of several devices, characters, settings, and thematic concerns. The narrative style of the story can be categorized by its stark and realistic tone that conveys the tense atmosphere of the colonial regime. The tone of the story shifts between innocence, vengeance, fear, and disappointment, highlighting the fragmented state of individuals and communities in a colonized era. The setting of the story is a tense and oppressive colonial environment marked by the imminent threat of violence.

The story unfolds in a city gripped by fear, where jets ominously hover in the sky, and deserted bazaars are patrolled by armed police.

The story begins with descriptive imagery of jets, “*For the past two or three days, planes had been hovering in the silent sky like Black hawks, their wings spread out as if in pursuit of prey*” which gives the readers the idea that there is some impending doom that is supposed to fall in a while. The image of an oppressed and fearful society is further clarified by using the narrative device of imagery such as “*Crimson windstorms prophesied the coming of a murderous tragedy*”. The description of the ongoing situation through use of language in the

beginning paragraph foreshadows the horrors of colonial oppression that reflects the collective anxiety of colonized as line “*Armed police patrolling the deserted bazaars made for a strange and frightening sight.*”

The controversial exchange of dialogues between the child, Khalid, and his father further elaborates the fragmented narrative of the story which can be seen as a frightful sight of the colonized. Below is a glimpse of it.

“*Seeing his father so troubled after reading the pamphlet, Khalid said worriedly, ‘Is it written on this paper that they will drop bombs on our house?’*”

‘*Khalid, you are excused now. Go! Play with your gun.*’

‘*But what is written on it?*’

‘*It’s written that this evening there will be a spectacle,*’ lied Khalid’s father”.

It shows the fragmented mindset of a fearful father who is trying to divert the attention of an innocent child who wants to understand the ongoing situation in his surroundings.

7.2. Literary Devices

The use of language by incorporating several literary devices in *A Spectacle* further adds to the themes of colonial violence, psychological trauma, and emotional damage to the colonized. One of the major literary devices used in the story is Irony. The very title of the story *A Spectacle* is ironic. Generally the concept of a spectacle is considered to be something that is seen as sort of entertainment, however in this story a massacre is turned into a Spectacle, where death and destruction is entertained by the colonizers and the colonized on the other hand are the silent and helpless spectators.

“*What spectacle?*” said Khalid’s father, hiding his fear.

‘*The spectacle which the planes were distributing advertises about this morning. The act has started, that is why we’re hearing the sound of firecrackers.*’

The readers know that what the small child consider as a Spectacle is in fact ‘a massacre’. Khalid’s father who understands the horrors that are about to happen, hides his fears and tells his son not to go outside. Khalid expects something amusing to happen, but the situation haunts him as he sees the bloodshed of a little child at the end of the story. This can be termed as situational irony, whereas audience awareness of the haunted situations of warfare while Khalid’s unawareness can be taken as dramatic irony.

In addition to the use of irony, another major device that readers can see throughout the story is the use of vivid imagery whether that is visual or auditory. The description of jets, “*hovering like black hawks,*” “*armed police patrolling the deserted bazaars,*” and “*crimson windstorm*” is an evident example of visual imagery. With the help of such language, the image of a frightened society can be constructed in the reader's mind.

Similarly, one can hear the sound of horror going around in the repressed colonial environment by reading the text where the author has used auditory imagery such as “*From far away, the painful screams of dogs could be heard. After a few moments those screams merged with the cries of human beings in agony,*” “*jet screamed passed overhead,*” “*the sound of a gunshot*” and so on.

Furthermore, the use of symbolism is also adding to the meaning of the text. The use of the word “*crimson*” at the beginning of the story symbolizes the upcoming bloodshed. Also can be taken as a foreshadowing technique. Moreover, the gun, as a tool of violence, symbolizes the urge of the colonized to show resistance and liberate themselves. However, the theme of oppression is more prominent in a colonized society, which can be seen by adding the adjective “*toy*” with the word “*gun*”, which shows the helplessness of individuals as well as the entire community. The “*jets screaming past overhead*” symbolize the power and threat of colonial rule.

Apart from these major devices, one can see personification as “*windstorms prophesied the coming of a murderous tragedy*”, and “*city was shrouded in an unknown fear*” as well as satire as “*out of fear of the king, he did not dare lift this boy off the road and lie him down on the front platform of the nearby shop*”. Overall, all these devices deepen the impact of pain and trauma that the colonized had to go through in the colonial regime.

7.3. Characterization

Khalid, a six-year-old protagonist of the story is an innocent child who is in the crossfire of colonial violence. His misunderstanding of the events around him shows the innocent mindset of the child which can't grasp the intensity of the situation. This can be seen when he considers the “*pamphlets*” dropped by

the jets as “*advert*” for an entertaining spectacle, as the line “*Abba, let's go! The spectacle must have begun!*”. However, the deep psychological trauma, fear, and distorted perception is so internalized in the mind of a young child that he wants to take revenge and defend themselves against the imagined threats as the text shows “*he watched the jets intently so that when they dropped a bomb, he could strike them down with the help of his air gun*”. Nevertheless, his innocence at the end of the story overshadows his desire to get vengeance, when he sees the bleeding child and considers it as some sort of punishment from the headmaster for not completing the homework, as “*Allah Mian! I pray that you give a fitting punishment to the teacher who has beaten the boy. Take away the cane he uses, the one which draws blood. I haven't memorized my times tables, so I'm afraid that the same cane might end up in my teacher's hand. If you don't heed my words, I won't speak to you either.*”

Khalid's father is another major character of the story who is the perfect picture of a subdued colonized resident whose personality is grappled in overall fear and resignation as the text, “*What spectacle?*” said Khalid's father, *hiding his fear,*” shows. His inability to reassure his son can be taken as his internalized fear that one could see in the entire colonized mass. He lies to his son about the pamphlet, saying “*It's written that this evening there will be a spectacle,*” to hide the truth from him, while deep down he pale reaction to the pamphlets, “*he now saw the looming tragedy in sharp focus*” foreshadows the upcoming tragedy. Khalid's father is that helpless colonized who is experiencing deep psychological turmoil but is unable to show resistance for the fear of great damages. “*Out of fear of the King, he did not dare lift this boy off the road*”.

The injured boy, lying wounded in the marketplace, is another symbol of oppressed colonized that are brutalized still no one gives attention.

The colonial regime inhumanity can be seen in the text, “*Blood spurting out*”, along with the manipulative techniques of colonizers who apparently would give place to the abandoned while in reality, they are the main causes of it, as “*The government authorities had provided ironclad vehicles to carry away any homeless, unclaimed, or abandoned individuals.*” The refusal of the bystanders to help the boy highlights the collective paralysis caused by systematic oppression, as the text,

"Ah! Death is dreadful, but oppression is even more terrifying and dreadful than death" shows.

7.4. Fanon's Theory of Violence and Its Application

The postcolonial aspect of violence has been explained in the theoretical framework section, where according to the theorist, Frantz Fanon, colonialism is inherently violent leaving deep physical and psychological scars on the bodies and minds of the colonized, and so in reaction to this oppression, they are also supposed to show resistance whether physically by becoming violent or mentally by showing resistance by other means such as thoughts, or submission, or obeying. In this story, we see both these aspects as an act of violence from the colonizers and in response to that a reaction from the colonizers.

i. Colonial Violence as a mechanism of control

Fanon argues that colonial violence is systematic, and is supposed to control the lives and mindsets of colonized to maintain dominance. In the story *A Spectacle*, the description of "hovering jets", "armed police", and "bloody massacre" are direct manifestations of the colonizers' violence.

The oppressed atmosphere of the city as, "For the past two or three days, planes had been hovering in the silent sky like black hawks, their wings spread out as if in pursuit of prey" highlights the basic concept of colonial violence as if the colonizers are the black hawks, lurking around to hunt the colonized. This predatory nature of colonial power is seen from the perspective of Fanon's theory of violence, which suggests the dehumanizing act of the masses to reduce them to a mere level of prey hiding from the predator or the objects to surrender.

The distribution of pamphlets as a warning from the king against a public assembly is another sign of colonial violent rule which diminishes the democratic rights of colonized to take a stand from themselves. "This pamphlet clearly stated that the King did not give permission for any public assembly, and if one was organized against his wishes, the subjects themselves would be responsible for the consequences". This act of oppression from Fanon's perspective is "psychic violence" that complement physical repression. Nevertheless, the opposition of king's order give way to physical violence as voice of the gunshots "Rat-a-tat-tat" could

be heard at the end of the story, which resulted in "The corpse of this innocent youth that had fallen victim to the blade of their tyranny".

ii. Colonized violence as a means of resistance

Fanon also views violence as means of resistance against oppression to liberate oneself. Although the story does not depict the scenes of organized violence, however the naïve struggles of a young child to take revenge through his air gun show the psychological state of the colonized and the human desire to show resistance and fight against oppression.

"Pulling out the air gun, he started target practice so that on the day the plane people dropped their bombs, he wouldn't miss. He would exact his full revenge. If only this innocent desire for vengeance could be instilled in every person!"

For Fanon, the inevitability of repression emerges as a response to colonial oppression. Colonial violence is so pervasive that it becomes normalized even for the most innocent minds to defend themselves against imagined threats. "The signs of unwavering intention and determination were visible on the face of the six-year-old child, who would have put a brave soldier to shame from the way he held his pretend gun". Fanon argues that such acts, however small, represent the beginnings of a liberationist consciousness.

Another major incident that suggests the resistance of colonized is the gathering of a public assembly against the king's warnings, as "People were leaving to take part in the public assembly". The collective resistance is a major fear of colonizers this is why they try to split them so they can never be together. However, as the theory suggests that resistance against oppression is so inevitable that even after the king's threat, the people were so eager to gather that they shut all of their workplaces, as "the spectacle must be exceptionally interesting to get all the shops closed down".

7.5. *A Spectacle* as Trauma Literature of South Asia

Saadat Hasan Manto's *A Spectacle* showcases the characteristics of trauma literature within the South Asian context. The text highlights the collective and individual psychological scars caused by colonial violence and British rule on the Subcontinent. The story shows political and social upheaval that has disrupted lives and caused trauma across generations. Trauma literature, as we all know, highlights the

experiences of individuals and societies that are grappled with catastrophic events which has shattered their normal lifestyles and so they are left with fragmented memories, suppressed emotions, and could not articulate their experiences. In South Asian context, trauma literature usually addresses 'the violence of colonial rule', 'the horrors of Partition in 1947', 'postcolonial conflicts, and 'the aftermaths of colonialism'.

The story *A Spectacle* is situated in the historical context of colonial South Asia, where state violence was so sporadic, that it left numerous with different types of scars. The hovering jets are representatives of the colonial power that created a sense of dread, "For the past two or three days, planes had been hovering in the silent sky like black hawks."

The pamphlets, with their threats of upcoming bloodshed, also deepen the atmosphere of dread. We see throughout the story, how this horror has become a major part of the lives that even if they want, they could not escape it. Readers came across different types of trauma while reading the story.

In trauma literature, children are often depicted as the witnesses of violence, whose innocence is shattered by the brutality of colonial oppression. In the story, we see an innocent young child who internalizes societal anxieties by seeing the planes hovering over their heads for days: "Abba, I am really afraid of these jets. Tell the plane people not to fly over our house". He observes his father who is a fearful colonized individual, and later sees an injured child lying helplessly on the road, "Abba, Abba, a boy has fallen down in the bazaar. His leg is bleeding so much". This compels one to think about the future of this child. What would become of him? How would he inherit this trauma? Will this intergenerational trauma surround him for his lifetime? Whether he would be a stable individual pursuing his dreams, or else his life would always be haunted by the nightmares he encountered in his childhood.

The next to this child is a silent father who represent the perfect picture of a helpless colonized. Khalid's father, overwhelmed by the fear, mainly remains silent and passive throughout the story. "His father's face turned white as paper. With great difficulty, he could only utter a single word: 'Gunshot!'" He is unable to process or confront the violence going on around him, which can be seen as major response to trauma.

Readers also came across a rational mother who is trying to protect her son from the horrors of colonial violence. Khalid's mother tries to shield him from the harsh realities of their lives by diverting his attention and ignoring his questions. She attempts to normalize the boy's injury by telling him that his master may have struck him for not completing the homework. "The cane must have struck him hard".

The injured boy lying helplessly on the road is another victim of colonial violence, who is supposed to carry the physical scars of colonial violence with himself throughout his life, in case he lives. This sense of disability may cause him severe emotional and psychological trauma in the future. In another case, his tragic death in this state of helplessness on the road could be picturized as a brutal face of colonial regime. The below passage from the text depicts it all in a beautiful manner, as

"The corpse of this innocent youth that had fallen victim to the blade of their tyranny, the sapling that had been crushed by their own hands, that unfurling bud that had withered before it could blossom by virtue of the poisonous air they had unleashed, the peace of someone's heart that had been snatched away by their oppression, now lies on a road constructed by them . . .".

Through the portrayal of different characters, their behaviors, along with the use of language, the text shows how trauma infiltrates every aspect of life, leaving an edible mark on individuals and communities.

Conclusion

While analyzing the text of Saadat Hasan Manto's *A Spectacle* through Fanon's theory of violence and situating it within the broader framework of trauma literature and postcolonial theory, this research highlights the enduring scars of colonial oppression and the repercussions of colonial violence. This duality of violence – its use as a means of control, and a response as resistance, can be seen in the story's portrayal of fear, resistance, and the ultimate cost of survival. The textual analysis of the story through its language, devices, characters give close insights about the narrative.

Furthermore, this research situates the story within trauma literature of South Asia, by referencing it to historical context. In conclusion, this short story is a crucial reminder of the challenges faced by individuals

as well as communities and entire societies in the colonial regime. By examining such works, we not only preserve the historical realities of the time but also give critical insights into the current situations of the world and our surroundings.

References

- Aghamelu, F. C., & Ejike, E. C.** (2017). Understanding Fanon's theory of violence and its relevance to contemporary violence in Africa. *Igwebuike: African Journal of Arts and Humanities*.
- Ndayisenga, Z.** (2022). Fanon on the arbitrariness of using violence: An inevitable for both colonialism and decolonization. *Journal of Black Studies*.
- Kebede, M.** (2001). The rehabilitation of violence and the violence of rehabilitation: Fanon and colonialism.
- Lye, John.** (1998). *Contemporary Literary Theory*, Brock University.
- Jha, B. K.** (1974). Fanon's theory of violence: A critique. *The Indian Journal of Political Science*, 35(4), 375-388.
- Fanon, F.** (1963). *The wretched of the earth* (C. Farrington, Trans.). Grove Press. (Original work published 1961).
- Dr. Sawant, D. G.** (2011). *Perspectives on Post-colonial Theory: Said, Spivak and Bhabha*.
- Rabaka, R.** (2010). Revolutionary Fanonism: On Frantz Fanon's Modification of Marxism and Decolonization of Democratic Socialism.
- Wallerstein, Immanuel M.** (1970). *Frantz Fanon: Reason and Violence*.
- Fashina, O.** (1989). Frantz Fanon and the ethical justification of anti-colonial violence.
- Mambrol, N.** (2016). *Frantz Fanon 's Contribution to Postcolonial Criticism*.
- Silverman, M.** (2009). *Frantz Fanon: Colonialism and Violence*.
- Young, R. J. C.** (2001). *Postcolonialism: An historical introduction*. Blackwell Publishers.

